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Customer engagement and customer loyalty: Evidence from selected HEI's students customers of iced coffee shops in Valencia City

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Abstract

This study explored the relationship between customer engagement and customer loyalty among college students who consume iced coffee shops in Valencia City, Bukidnon. It examined three dimensions of engagement—cognitive, emotional, and behavioral—and their impact on loyalty, focusing on factors such as customer demographics, purchase behaviors, and interaction patterns. Using quantitative, descriptive, and correlational research methods, this study analyzed data from 370 respondents representing students from three local higher education institutions (HEIs). Guided by the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) Theory, alongside the Affective-Behavioral-Cognitive (ABC) Model and Self-Determination Theory (SDT), the research framework linked cognitive evaluations, emotional connections, and behavioral patterns to sustained customer loyalty. The study employed validated survey instruments and statistical tools to ensure reliability and precision. Key findings revealed that customer loyalty—characterized by repeat purchases—was significantly influenced by customer engagement levels. Emotional engagement stood out as a critical driver, highlighting the role of positive interactions and mood in fostering brand attachment. The study aimed to help coffee shop owners design engagement strategies to enhance loyalty, improve customer retention, and differentiate their offerings in a competitive market. It also contributed valuable insights into customer behavior in the coffee industry, laying the groundwork for future research on consumer dynamics.

Keywords: Customer engagement; Customer loyalty; Customer engagement cognitive; Customer engagement emotional/affective; Customer engagement behavioral; College students; Iced coffee shops

1. Introduction

Cultivating customer loyalty presents significant challenges for businesses, particularly those in the coffee shop sector, as the process is dynamic. Consumers assess some factors before pledging their loyalty to a coffee shop. Maintaining loyal customers in every coffee shop for various positive outcomes is crucial (Yiğit and Perçin, 2021; Sathish and Venkatesakumar, 2011). Customer loyalty is a critical asset for the business (Godovykh and Tasci, 2021; Han *et al.*, 2018).

According to Hur *et al.* (2020), customer loyalty is not just about the price or the availability it is also about the emotional connection. Modern customers want to feel seen, heard, and valued—they want to avoid meeting their needs (Woodland, 2024). This requires owners to prioritize emotional relationships over transactional interactions. Establishing emotional connections secures customer loyalty. Loyal customers are valuable assets for any brand as they are likelier to choose the brand over the competition, spend more, and generate more significant transactions. Engaged customers

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are loyal customers (Woodland, 2024) the more the customers are engaged with the brand, the more loyal they are to repeat their product purchase.

Customer engagement is essential for the coffee shop as it promotes customer loyalty, increases sales, and improves the overall customer experience. Engaged customers tend to return, spend more, and contribute to continued business growth. Coffee shop owners can establish lasting relationships and set themselves apart in a highly competitive market (Sharma, 2024). Additionally, Sharma (2024) stated that effective customer engagement in coffee shops will significantly increase customer loyalty. In contrast, a coffee shop with effective customer engagement may need help in understanding its customers' preferences, leading to poor customer experience and disconnection, causing them to turn to competitors who make them feel more valued.

Several past studies have observed a direct effect of customer engagement on customer experience and loyalty (Arrfat, 2020; Safitri *et al.*, 2020). Researchers have suggested that customer engagement comprises cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components (Islam *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2019). Maintaining strong customer relationships and ensuring business longevity can be accomplished through the cultivation of customer loyalty, a vital business asset (Song, Wang, and Han, 2019). The potential contribution of customer engagement to customer loyalty is becoming known in the literature (Bowden, 2009). However, the specific dynamics and mechanisms underlying this relationship in the coffee shop sector warrant further exploration. Given the industry's highly competitive nature, it is crucial to understand how coffee shop owners can prioritize emotional relationships over transactional interactions to establish a lasting customer base (Woodland, 2024).

This study aims to determine the relationship and influence between customer engagement and customer loyalty among selected HEI students who are customers of iced coffee shops in Valencia City. Specifically, it seeks to answer several sub-problems.

First, the study examines the frequency of the demographic profiles of selected HEI students, considering factors such as age, sex, school attended, year level, and the last iced coffee shop they visited. Second, it evaluates the level of agreement of these students regarding customer loyalty (CL) and different aspects of customer engagement, including cognitive (CEC), emotional/affective (CEE), and behavioral (CEB) engagement.

Additionally, the study investigates whether there is a significant difference between the demographic profile of selected HEI students and customer loyalty. It also explores whether significant differences exist between the demographic profile and customer engagement in terms of cognitive, emotional/affective, and behavioral engagement.

Furthermore, the research seeks to determine whether there is a significant relationship between customer loyalty and customer engagement, considering cognitive, emotional/affective, and behavioral aspects. Lastly, it aims to identify whether customer loyalty significantly influences customer engagement in these three dimensions.

Based on the statement of the problem, this study proposes the following hypotheses:

- H01: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of selected HEI students who are customers of iced coffee shops in Valencia City and customer loyalty.
- H02: There is no significant difference between the demographic profile of selected HEI students who are customers of iced coffee shops in Valencia City and customer engagement.
- H03: There is no significant relationship between customer loyalty and customer engagement in terms of cognitive engagement (CEC), emotional/affective engagement (CEE), and behavioral engagement (CEB).
- H04: There is no significant influence between customer loyalty and customer engagement in terms of cognitive engagement (CEC), emotional/affective engagement (CEE), and behavioral engagement (CEB).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

Quantitative Research connotes the relationship between the independent and dependent variables (Mehrad and Tahriri, 2019). To assess these variables accurately, a descriptive study requires hundreds or thousands of respondents.

Descriptive Research involves describing and observing the phenomenon without influencing the variables and is used for gathering numerical data (Siedlecki, 2020). According to Iranifard and Roudsari (2022), Comparative Research is

the study of differences and similarities between two cases; the researcher then compares the particular issue with different contexts, either quantitative or qualitative approaches.

Correlational Research Design examines the differences of two or more variables, and variables are not manipulated (Queirós *et al.*, 2017). Correlational Research Design involves two or more quantitative variables subjected to the computation of variables to see if there is a relationship between variables (Mohajan, 2020).

2.2. Research Instrument

The researcher conducted a pilot test by gathering thirty respondents who are college students from selected HEIs who are engaging in buying iced coffee from iced coffee shops around Valencia City, Bukidnon.

The researcher used Cronbach's Alpha test score to assess the reliability and validity of the construct and the average item values of each construct to determine the level of agreement. This study used stratified random sampling. Stratified random sampling divides the population into several layers and then randomly samples from the parent population. This narrows the difference between different types of individuals through classification. The complete pilot testing survey is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Construct Description, Source, and Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Score Result from a Pilot Test of Thirty (30) Samples

Construct	Description	Source	Cronbach's Alpha (Reliability Score from Pilot Test)	Remarks
Customer Loyalty (CL)	The customer's long-term devotion to the product can be both behavioral and attitudinal commitment to the product.	Whence customer loyalty? (Oliver, 1999).	0.942	All eight item questions are higher than the 0.70 reliability score.
Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC)	The level of customers' processing of brand-related thoughts in brand interaction.	Consumer brand engagement in social media: conceptualization, scale development and validation Hollebeek, L.D., Glynn, M.S. and Brodie, R.J. (2014).	0.889	All eight item questions are higher than the 0.70 reliability score.
Customer Engagement Emotional (CEE)	The degree of customers' positive interaction with brand-related affect	Consumer brand engagement in social media: conceptualization, scale development and validation Hollebeek, L.D., Glynn, M.S. and Brodie, R.J. (2014).	0.930	All eight item questions are higher than the 0.70 reliability score.
Customer Engagement Behavioral (CEB)	The level of energy customers exert and express towards the brand.	Consumer brand engagement in social media: conceptualization, scale development and validation Hollebeek, L.D., Glynn, M.S. and Brodie, R.J. (2014).	0.945	All eight item questions are higher than the 0.70 reliability score.
Overall Cronbach's Alpha		0.981		All 32-item questions are higher than the 0.70 reliability score.

Table 1 shows Cronbach's Alpha Results for Pilot Testing; the eight customer loyalty question items have a reliability analysis of 0.942. Customer engagement cognitive has a reliability analysis of 0.889. Customer engagement emotional/affective has a reliability analysis of 0.930. Customer engagement behavioral has a reliability analysis of 0.945. The overall Cronbach's Alpha score for the pilot study is 0.981.

Table 2 Construct Item Questions to be Used in Actual Data Gathering

Construct	Item Questions	Adapted From	Total No. of Item Questions	Total No. of Item Questions Deleted After Pilot Test
Customer Loyalty (CL)	CL1. I try to visit my usual iced coffee shop every time I need to freshen up.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).	8	0
	CL2. I will try to continue with my usual iced coffee shop in the coming years.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).		
	CL3. I will encourage my relatives and friends to become customers of this iced coffee shop.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).		
	CL4. I consider myself a loyal customer at my usual iced coffee shop.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).		
	CL5. I will give positive recommendations to others about my usual iced coffee shop.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		
	CL6. I will not buy another iced coffee drink other than at my usual iced coffee shop.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).		
	CL7. I will continue to enjoy drinks at my usual iced coffee shop.	Monferrer, D., Tena M. A. M., & Estrada, M. (2019).		
	CL8. I will buy in iced coffee shop most often.	Chaudhuri and Holbrook (2001).		
Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC)	CEC1. I asked myself questions to check if I liked the iced coffee at this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).	8	0
	CEC2. I spend much time thinking about the iced coffee at this iced coffee shop.	Rothbard, (2001).		
	CEC3. I make time to think about the iced coffee at this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).		
	CEC4. Time flies when I am drinking this iced coffee.	Rothbard, (2001).		
	CEC5. When drinking iced coffee at this iced coffee shop, I forgot everything else around me.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEC6. When I am drinking this iced coffee, I get carried away.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEC7. Consider this iced coffee shop as your first choice to buy iced coffee.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		

	CEC8. I seek ideas or information about the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	Vivek, (2009).		
Construct	Item Questions	Adapted From	Total No. of Item Questions	Total No. of Item Questions Deleted After Pilot Test
Customer Engagement Emotional (CEE)	CEE1. It made me happy to drink iced coffee at this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).	8	0
	CEE2. The iced coffee at the iced coffee shop had a positive impact on my mood.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).		
	CEE3. I care about this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).		
	CEE4. I feel enthusiastic about this iced coffee from this iced coffee shop.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEE5. I am interested in anything about this iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEE6. I find this iced coffee of this iced coffee shop interesting.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEE7. When drinking this iced coffee of this iced coffee shop, I feel happy.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
	CEE8. I get pleasure from drinking this iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	Schaufeli <i>et al.</i> , (2002).		
Customer Engagement Behavioral (CEB)	CEB1. I share my ideas about the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).	8	0
	CEB2. I share interesting content about the iced coffee of this iced coffee.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).		
	CEB3. I ask questions about the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	de Vreede, T., <i>et al.</i> , (2019).		
	CEB4. Encourage friends and relatives to buy iced coffee at this iced coffee shop.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		
	CEB5. I promote the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		
	CEB6. I try to get others interested in the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		

	CEB7. I actively defend the iced coffee of this iced coffee shop from its critics.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		
Construct	Item Questions	Adapted From	Total No. of Item Questions	Total No. of Item Questions Deleted After Pilot Test
	CEB8. Recommend this iced coffee shop to someone who seeks your advice in buying iced coffee.	Zeithaml, V., Berry, L. & Parasuraman, A. (1996); Bloemer, J., Odekerken-Schröder, G. & Kestens, L. (2003).		

Table 2 shows the construct item questions used in actual data gathering. Eight-item questions were used for customer loyalty, eight-item questions were used for customer engagement cognitively, eight-item questions were used for customer engagement emotional/affective, and eight-item questions were used for customer engagement behaviorally. A total of 32-item questions were used in this study.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct reliability is involved with consistency, respondents' performance on the survey, and reproducibility. It is the total consistency of a certain measure; a measure is considered highly reliable when it results the same under consistent conditions. Construct Validity is when practical tests derived from a theory are used to measure some construct defined by the theory; it is used when you are measuring something that cannot be directly observed. The importance of both Construct Reliability and Construct Validity makes a stronger assessment of the Test or tool and conducting it in different ways makes for a stronger evaluation (Emerson, 2024).

Table 3 Reliability and Validity Test of the Research Instrument

Standard Value		>0.5	>0.6	>0.5	> or = to 0.7
Construct	Item	FL	CR	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC)	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive1	0.609	0.869	0.456	0.922
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive2	0.734			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive3	0.715			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive4	0.690			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive5	0.709			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive6	0.580			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive7	0.749			
	Customer_Engagement_Cognitive8	0.593			

Customer Engagement Emotional (<i>CEE</i>)	Customer_Engagement_Emotional1	0.756	0.891	0.505	0.927
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional2	0.691			
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional3	0.741			
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional4	0.618			
Standard Value		>0.5	>0.6	>0.5	> or = to 0.7
Construct	Item	FL	CR	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional5	0.680			
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional6	0.696			
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional7	0.767			
	Customer_Engagement_Emotional8	0.725			
Customer Engagement Behavioral (<i>CEB</i>)	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 1	0.525	0.858	0.434	0.920
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 2	0.678			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 3	0.832			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 4	0.603			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 5	0.621			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 6	0.687			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 7	0.574			
	Customer_Engagement_Behavioral 8	0.704			
Customer Loyalty (<i>CL</i>)	Customer_Loyalty1	0.613	0.852	0.419	0.921
	Customer_Loyalty2	0.615			
	Customer_Loyalty3	0.708			
	Customer_Loyalty4	0.625			
	Customer_Loyalty5	0.686			

	Customer_Loyalty6	0.56 5			
	Customer_Loyalty7	0.65 1			
	Customer_Loyalty8	0.70 1			
Overall, Alpha for Customer Engagement*					0.972
Overall, Alpha (ALL 32 Item Questions) **					0.979

*24 item questions for Customer Engagement (CEC, CEE, CEB) **Overall alpha, 32 item questions, no item questions deleted.

Table 3 presents the results of the reliability and validity test conducted based on the research instrument, an adopted questionnaire used to assess customer engagement relationships and influence on customer loyalty. With a Factor Loading (FL) of 0.609, Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC) exhibited a good correlation with the construct; its Composite Reliability (CR) was 0.869; its Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was 0.456 the value is below the suggested value which is the 0.50; and its Cronbach's Alpha was 0.922 which was superior. With a Factor Loading (FL) of 0.756, Customer Engagement Emotional (CEE) exhibited a good correlation with the construct; its Composite Reliability (CR) was 0.891; its Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was 0.505, the value is above the suggested value which is the 0.50; and its Cronbach's Alpha was 0.927 which was superior. With a Factor Loading (FL) of 0.525, Customer Engagement Behavioral (CEB) exhibited a good correlation with the construct; its Composite Reliability (CR) was 0.858; its Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was 0.434 the value is below the suggested value which is the 0.50; and its Cronbach's Alpha was 0.920 which was superior. With a Factor Loading (FL) of 0.613, Customer Loyalty (CL) exhibited a good correlation with the construct; its Composite Reliability (CR) was 0.852; its Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was 0.419 the value is below the suggested value, which is the 0.50; and its Cronbach's Alpha was 0.921 which was superior. The overall Cronbach's Alpha for Customer Engagement (CE) of 0.972 was superior, and with the overall Cronbach Alpha value of 0.079, the research instrument has outstanding overall reliability, indicating great internal consistency across all constructs.

3.2. Significant Research Results

Table 4 presents the result of problem 1's statement, which is the frequency of the demographic profile of selected HEI student customers of iced coffee shops in Valencia City in terms of age, sex, school attended, year level, and iced coffee last visited.

Demographic Profile in Terms of Frequency

Table 4 Demographic Profiling of the Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18 to 20 years old	191	51.6
	21 to 25 years old	175	47.3
	26 to 30 years old	4	1.1
Sex	Male	129	34.9
	Female	241	65.1
School Attended	ACLC College of Bukidnon, Inc.	37	10.0
	Philippine Colleges Foundation	148	40.0
	Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon), Inc.	185	50.0
Year Level	1st Year	111	30.0
	2nd Year	151	40.8
	3rd Year	42	11.4
	4th Year	66	17.8

Iced Coffee Shop Last Visited	Don Macchiatos	304	82.2
	Beanukid Bake & Brew	10	2.7
	M310 Cà Phê	2	0.5
	Café Luiza	1	0.3
	Daru Café & Ranch	8	2.2
	Coffee Clock	38	10.3
	Other: JZM	1	0.3
	Other: Haven's Cafe and Tea	1	0.3
	Other: Da Rendezvous	2	0.5
	Other: Suok Cafe	1	0.3
	Other: Changtea	1	0.3
	Other: K-Kopi	1	0.3
<i>Note: n=370</i>			

Table 4 presented that 51.6% of respondents between the ages of 18 and 20 had answered the questionnaire, followed by 47.3% between the ages of 21 and 25 and 1.1% between the ages of 26 and 30. As a result, most respondents (51.6%) were between 18 and 20. The table shows that 34.9% of the respondents were male, and 65.1% were female. As a result, most respondents (51.6%) were female. The table shows that 10% of the respondents were from ACLC College of Bukidnon, Inc., 40% were from the Philippine Colleges Foundation, and 50% were from Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon), Inc. As a result, most respondents (50%) were from Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon) Inc. The table presented that 30% of the respondents were 1st-year students, 40.8% were 2nd-year students, 11.4% were 3rd-year students, and 17.8% were 4th-year students. As a result, most respondents (40.8%) were 2nd year students. The table presented 82.2% of the respondents last visited iced coffee shop were Don Macchiatos, 2.7% visited Beanukid Bake & Brew, 0.5% visited M310 Cà Phê, 0.3% visited Café Luiza, 2.2% visited Daru Café & Ranch, 10.3% visited Coffee Clock, 0.3% visited JZM, 0.3% visited Haven's Cafe and Tea, 0.5% visited Da Rendezvous, 0.3% visited Suok Café, 0.3% visited Changtea and 0.3% visited K-Kopi. As a result, most respondents (82.2%) last visited Don Macchiatos.

Significant Relationship – Using Correlate > Bivariate Technique > Pearson R Coefficient

Correlation Analysis is used to evaluate the strength and direction of the linear relationship between variables; it helps understand whether an increase in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in another (Hasiloglu & Kunduraci, 2018). The bivariate technique is a subset of correlation analysis that focuses on the relationship between exactly two variables; it evaluates how one variable behaves in response to changes in another (Hasiloglu & Kunduraci, 2018). Pearson R Coefficient uses a linear relationship between two variables; a value close to +1 indicates a strong positive correlation, a value close to -1 indicates a strong negative correlation and a value near 0 implies no significant linear relationship (Hasiloglu & Kunduraci, 2018).

Table 5 The Relationship Between Customer Engagement (Overall) and Customer Loyalty at Iced Coffee Shops Perceived by the Respondents in Selected HEIs School in Valencia City, Bukidnon

Construct	Me an	Std. Dev.	(1)	(2)	Interpretation DV to IV (1)		Remarks
					According to Hair et al. (2013)	According to Cohen (1988) ^a	
(1) Customer Loyalty (DV)	5.449	1.060	(0.921)				
(2) Customer Engagement as Overall (IV)	5.400	1.022	.938**	(0.972)	Very Strong Positive Correlation	Large Positive Relationship	H ₀₃ NOT accepted

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). a Direction and Strength of the variables' relationship; Values in the diagonal with parenthesis are the Cronbach's Alpha; n=370

Table 5 represents the relationship between customer engagement (IV) and customer loyalty (DV) at iced coffee shops, as respondents from selected HEIs in Valencia City, Bukidnon perceived. A strong positive correlation of 0.938** was observed using the Pearson R coefficient, indicating a significant association between the two variables at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). This coefficient suggests a large positive relationship, per Cohen's (1988) interpretation guidelines, meaning that higher customer engagement is associated with increased customer loyalty. The Cronbach's Alpha values (shown diagonally) validate the reliability of the constructs measured, with customer loyalty at 0.921 and customer engagement at 0.972, implying strong internal consistency. Given these results, the null hypothesis (Ho3) is not accepted, reinforcing the claim that customer engagement significantly influences customer loyalty with in this result.

Table 6 The Relationship Between CEC, CEE, and CEB to Customer Loyalty at Iced Coffee Shops Perceived by the Respondents in Selected HEIs School in Valencia City, Bukidnon

	Construct	Mean	Std. Dev.	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	Interpretation DV to IV (1)		Re-marks
								According to Hair <i>et al.</i> (2013)	According to Cohen (1988) ^a	
1.	Customer Loyalty (DV)	5.449	1.060	(0.921)						
2.	Customer Engagement Cognitive CEC (IV)	5.373	1.071	.904**	(0.922)			Very Strong Positive Correlation	Large Positive Relationship	H _{o3} NOT accepted
3.	Customer Engagement Emotional CEE (IV) ^b	5.460	1.031	.911**	.905**	(0.927)		Very Strong Positive Correlation	Large Positive Relationship	H _{o3} NOT accepted
4.	Customer Engagement Behavioral CEB (IV)	5.369	1.074	.901**	.909**	.881**	(0.920)	Very Strong Positive Correlation	Large Positive Relationship	H _{o3} NOT accepted

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).; aDirection and Strength of the variables' relationship; Values in the diagonal with parenthesis are the Cronbach's Alpha; bCustomer Engagement Emotional CEE obtained the highest correlation (Pearson R Coefficient = 0.911 and p-value = 0.01); n=370

Table 6 represents the relationships between three dimensions of customer engagement—cognitive (CEC), emotional (CEE), and behavioral (CEB)—and customer loyalty at iced coffee shops, as perceived by respondents in selected HEIs in Valencia City, Bukidnon. Each dimension shows a strong positive correlation with customer loyalty, with Pearson R coefficients of 0.904, 0.911, and 0.901, respectively, all significant at the 0.01 level. The emotional engagement dimension (CEE) has the highest correlation (0.911), suggesting it is the most influential factor among the three in fostering customer loyalty. Cronbach's Alpha values (diagonally displayed) confirm high reliability, with scores above 0.92 for each construct. According to Cohen's (1988) standards and the interpretations provided in Table 2.5 and Table 2.6, these coefficients reflect large positive relationships, indicating that stronger engagement across cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions aligns with higher customer loyalty. Consequently, the null hypothesis (Ho3) is not accepted, emphasizing the significant impact of each engagement dimension on loyalty.

Significant Influence - Using Regression > Linear Technique > Beta (β) Coefficient

R (Correlation Coefficient) quantifies the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables with values ranging from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to +1 (perfect positive correlation). An R-value close to 0 indicates no linear correlation (University of Florida). R² (Coefficient of Determination) indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variables in the model (University of Florida). Adjusted R² corrects R² by penalizing the number of predictors, ensuring a more accurate measure of explanatory power. It increases only if adding a new variable improves the model more than expected by chance (University of Florida). Durbin-Watson tests for autocorrelation in residuals; a value near 2 suggests no autocorrelation, while values significantly below 2 indicate positive autocorrelation, and those above 2 suggest negative autocorrelation (University of Florida).

Table 7 Simple Linear Regression (Enter Method) Analysis on Significant Predictors of Variables Customer Engagement and Customer Loyalty

Model	Variables	Standardized Coefficients (β)**	t	p-value	Collinearity Tolerance*	VIF*	Hypothesis Decision	Remarks
1.	(Constant): Customer Loyalty (DV)							
	Customer Engagement Cognitive (IV)	0.904	40.586	0.000	1.000	1.000	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty
2.	(Constant): Customer Loyalty (DV)							
	Customer Engagement Cognitive (IV)	0.439	9.773	0.000	0.182	5.503	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty
	Customer Engagement Emotional CEE (IV)	0.514	11.444	0.000	0.182	5.503	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty
3.	(Constant): Customer Loyalty (DV)							
	Customer Engagement Cognitive (IV)	0.245	4.824	0.000	0.126	7.940	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty
	Customer Engagement Emotional CEE (IV)**	0.411	9.159	0.000	0.162	6.191	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty
	Customer Engagement Behavioral CEB (IV)	0.316	6.877	0.000	0.155	6.466	H_0 NOT accepted	Significantly influences Customer Loyalty

Note: n = 370; Test of Normality - passed; Test of Collinearity - passed; Number of Samples - passed (greater than 200); Homoscedasticity - passed; Constant to all Models. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty; *Multi-collinearity issue - check Tolerance value should be more than 0.3 and VIF value should be less than 4. In this case, there was a slight multi-collinearity issue because VIF was higher than 4 and Tolerance values were lower than 0.3.; **As to Model 3, the main factor that influenced customer loyalty was customer engagement emotional CEE ($\beta=0.411$ and p-value = 0.000). It was followed by customer engagement behavioral CEB ($\beta=0.285$ and p-value = 0.000).; Lastly, customer engagement cognitive CEC ($\beta=0.245$ and p-value=0.000). All dimensions of the customer engagement concept were found to significantly influence customer loyalty in selected iced coffee shops visited by the respondents.

Table 7 represents the results of a simple linear regression analysis, examining how different dimensions of customer engagement (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral) predict customer loyalty at iced coffee shops. The analysis used three models, each with customer loyalty as the dependent variable. Model 1 indicates that cognitive engagement significantly influences loyalty, with a high standardized coefficient ($\beta = 0.904$) and a p-value of 0.000. Model 2 adds emotional engagement as a predictor, showing that cognitive ($\beta = 0.439$) and emotional engagement ($\beta = 0.514$) significantly affect loyalty. Model 3 includes all three engagement types, identifying emotional engagement as the strongest predictor of loyalty ($\beta = 0.411$), followed by behavioral ($\beta = 0.316$) and cognitive ($\beta = 0.245$) engagement, all with p-values of 0.000. Despite some multicollinearity concerns (VIF > 4 in certain cases), the analysis confirms that each engagement type significantly impacts customer loyalty, with emotional engagement being the most influential. This suggests enhancing emotional connections could be key to fostering loyalty among iced coffee shop customers.

Table 8 Simple Linear Regression (Enter Method) Analysis on Significant Predictors of Variables Customer Engagement (Overall) and Customer Loyalty

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Durbin Watson*
1	0.938a	0.879	0.879	1.640

Note: n = 370; Test of Normality - passed; Test of Collinearity - passed; Number of Samples - passed (greater than 200); Homoscedasticity - passed a. Predictors: (Constant), Customer_Engagement_Mean Constant to all Models. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty *Autocorrelation issue - check Durbin-Watson value; it should be between 2 and 4. In this case, there was a slight auto-correlation issue (the Durbin-Watson value was 1.640) *The R-Square value tells how much of the variance in the DV was explained by the model. In this case, the value was 0.879 which means 87.90% of the variance in the customer engagement (overall) influenced the customer loyalty of selected HEIs school students in Valencia City, Bukidnon. In other words, this study's findings, which ranged 87.90%, fit the whole model used in the research.

Table 8 represents a simple linear regression analysis of the relationship between overall customer engagement and loyalty among HEI students in Valencia City, Bukidnon. The model shows a strong positive correlation (R = 0.938),

indicating a substantial link between customer engagement and loyalty. The R-squared value of 0.879 implies that 87.9% of the variance in customer loyalty is explained by customer engagement, demonstrating a high explanatory power of the model. An adjusted R-squared of 0.879 further confirms the model's strength. The Durbin-Watson value 1.640, while slightly below the ideal range (2–4), suggests minimal autocorrelation concerns. Overall, the findings suggest that customer engagement is a critical predictor of loyalty, explaining nearly 88% of loyalty behavior among students in the study. This high percentage underscores the effectiveness of fostering customer engagement to enhance loyalty within this demographic.

Table 9 Simple Linear Regression (Enter Method) Analysis on Significant Predictors of Variables Customer Engagement (Overall) and Customer Loyalty

Model	Variables	Standardized Coefficients (β)**	t	p-value	Collinearity Tolerance*	VIF*	Hypothesis Decision	Remarks
1	(Constant): Customer Loyalty (DV)							
	Overall Customer Engagement (IV)**	0.938	51.755	0.000	1.000	1.000	<i>H₀₄ NOT accepted</i>	<i>Significantly influences Customer Loyalty</i>

Note: n = 370; Test of Normality - passed; Test of Collinearity - passed; Number of Samples - passed (greater than 200); Homoscedasticity - passed Constant to all Models. Dependent Variable: Customer Engagement *Multi-collinearity issue - check Tolerance value should be more than 0.3 and VIF value should be less than 4. In this case, there was no multi-collinearity issue (The tolerance value was more than 0.3 and VIF values were less than 4.) **The total mean of three dimensions under the customer engagement concept showed that there was a significant influence on customer loyalty (p-value = 0.000).

Table 9 represents a simple linear regression analysis examining the impact of overall customer engagement on customer loyalty. The model demonstrates a strong positive influence, with a standardized coefficient (β) of 0.938, suggesting that customer engagement significantly predicts loyalty. The p-value of 0.000 confirms this relationship as statistically significant, leading to rejecting the null hypothesis (H₀₄). No multicollinearity issues were present, as indicated by a tolerance value above 0.3 and a VIF of 1.0. These results highlight that customer engagement effectively explains customer loyalty among respondents in the study. Additionally, the model passed tests for normality, collinearity, sample adequacy, and homoscedasticity, affirming its reliability. Thus, customer engagement appears to be a critical factor influencing loyalty, as supported by a strong statistical association in the analysis.

3.2.1. Significant Difference

Significant Difference – Customer Loyalty

- *Hypothesis Statement: H₀₁*: There is no significant difference between selected HEIs students’ customers of Iced Coffee in Valencia City demographic profile and customer loyalty.
- *Decision: H₀₁ NOT Accepted* in terms of Sex. *H₀₁ Accepted* in terms of Age, Year Level, and Iced Coffee Shop Last Visited. *H₀₁ NOT Accepted* in terms of School Attended, PCF compared to VCI group.

The third statement of the problem is the difference in the level of customer loyalty at ice coffee shops between male and female students with a p-value of 0.001. This confirms a statistically significant difference in customer loyalty between male and female students. Regarding the age groups, Age does not significantly influence the loyalty levels of students toward iced coffee shops in the studied demographic. However, the findings based on the school attended lead to partial acceptance and partial rejection, suggesting that school affiliation may play a minor role in influencing loyalty at iced coffee shops for certain institutions. The results imply that customer loyalty is consistent across different year levels. Lastly, for the iced coffee last visited, the level of customer loyalty among students remains consistent regardless of the specific iced coffee shop they most recently frequented. Notably, due to the small sample size in at least one group, post hoc tests for further exploration were not performed.

Based on the results, the study relates to the study of (Dillon *et al.*, 2019), which says women significantly use more caffeine than men, specifically female and male college students. According to Mahoney *et al.* (2019), females consume more caffeine than males. Also, the study of (Ng *et al.*, 2020) states that gender influences the individual's behavior, predicting the consumers' consumption choices. According to Bhatt *et al.* (2020), related to the school attended the location significantly affects customer loyalty. That makes location a primary element in building a business; locations that are easily accessible make it easy for the consumers to visit the business directly (Maranatha *et al.*, 2023). The

location has positively and significantly influenced customer loyalty (Hermanto *et al.*, 2019; Wirawan *et al.*, 2019; Dulkhatif *et al.*, 2016).

Significant Difference – Customer Engagement

Hypothesis Statement: H₀₂: There is no significant difference between selected HEIs students customers of Iced Coffee in Valencia City demographic profile and customer engagement.

Decision: H₀₂ NOT Accepted in terms of Sex for the overall Customer Engagement, Sex for CEC, Sex for CEE, and Sex for CEB. *H₀₂* Accepted in terms of Age for the overall Customer Engagement, Age for CEE, Age for CEB, School Attended for the overall Customer Engagement, School Attended for CEC, School Attended for CEB, Year Level for the overall Customer Engagement, Year Level for CEC, Year Level for CEE, Year Level for CEB, and the overall Customer Engagement for the Iced Coffee Shop Last Visited. *H₀₂* is NOT Accepted in terms of Age for the age group 18 to 20 years old and 21 to 25 years old. The school attended CEE and PCF for the CEC compared to ACLC and VCI groups.

The fourth problem statement is the difference in the level of customer engagement at ice coffee shops between male and female students, with a p-value of 0.000. This confirms a statistically significant difference in customer engagement between male and female students. Regarding customer engagement cognitive, both genders show significant differences with a p-value of 0.000, which shows how the students cognitively engage with iced coffee shop experiences. In customer engagement, emotional, both genders show significant influence with a p-value of 0.000. This suggests potential variations in how male and female students emotionally connect with these establishments, which is relevant for targeted marketing strategies. While in customer engagement behavioral, both genders show significant differences with a p-value of 0.001. This suggests that male and female students interact differently with iced coffee shops. There is no significant difference regarding the age group of the overall engagement, but with regards to the customer engagement cognitive, the ages between 18 to 20 years old and 21 to 25 years old have distinct differences from the other age groups because they have similar engagement perceptions. Meanwhile, in the age group, customer engagement and emotional engagement are relatively uniform across all age groups. Also, in the age group of customer engagement behavioral are generally consistent across all age groups. While in the overall school attended, there is no significant difference, which indicates a consistency of engagement level across these educational institutions. While in the school attended in customer engagement cognitive, there is no significant difference, which means it is consistent across the institution. However, in the schools attended in customer engagement, there is a partial acceptance and rejection of the hypothesis. Philippine Colleges Foundation students experience different emotional engagement levels at iced coffee shops compared to the other two schools, implying that emotional engagement varies based on the specific school environment location. While in the school attended in customer engagement, behavioral indicates no significant difference, implying that school affiliation has nothing to do with behavioral engagement. The overall engagement for the year level shows no significant difference. This shows that all year level has similar engagement with iced coffee shops. While the customer engagement cognitive for year level suggests that cognitive engagement in this setting is unaffected by the year level of the students, the same goes for emotional engagement, which posits no difference, as well as behavioral engagement. For the overall customer engagement, the last coffee shop visited did not significantly impact any aspect of customer engagement.

Based on the study of (Mahoney *et al.*, 2019), females consume more caffeine than males. According to Dillon *et al.* (2019), that says women have significantly used more caffeine than men, specifically female and male college students. Related to the study of (Gligor *et al.*, 2022), that says genders directly impact customer engagement activities such as cognitive, affective, and behavioral. Also, the study of (Ng *et al.*, 2020) states that gender influences the individual's behavior, predicting the consumers' consumption choices. Ng *et al.* (2020) also state that gender influences the consumer's cognitive and behavior. This area treated biological Sex as representative of an individual cognition; women's gender roles entail communal goals concerning both self and others, while men's gender roles focus only on the self. Gender and emotional aspects influence how consumers respond to emotion when interacting. Generation Z consume cold coffee or iced coffee (Winsight, 2020). Another study by (Wibowo *et al.*, 2023) found that Gen Z prefers cold blended coffee and prefers to consume coffee in coffee shops with a wide selection of variants. People aged 18-25 years significantly declared coffee consumption than other age group consumers (Czarniecka-Skubina *et al.*, 2021). In relation to the previous study by Lone *et al.* (2022), the Age ranged from 18 to 25 years old, coffee consumption was significantly higher than that of other age groups, and coffee consumption has been positively associated with Age in several studies. Gen Y and Gen Z are still college students; young consumers are often involved in analytical and imaginative thoughts toward the brands (Han *et al.*, 2019; Sarkar *et al.*, 2019; Garg *et al.*, 2015). According to Sharma and Srivastav (2023), ages in different generations have different relationships with people and their preferences in the products they are using or consuming. In order to have a deeper connection with the customers, companies are fostering studies to better understand the target markets by analyzing their preferences. (Brooks, 2022) states that Gen Z is fast

knocking into adulthood, and they have their own style and preferences wherein they have their unique way of purchasing and consuming; even in the same generation, there are still age gaps between their choices. Concerning customer engagement with the specific school affiliation, it supports the study of Menon and Khan (2002), where emotional attachment is the subjective response of consumers to environmental stimuli. Emotional connection results in repurchase and revisit intention by the consumers; it could lead to perceived value where the customers' consumption decision-making to revisit the shop will be affected (Lin and Chao, 2023). Another factor related to the students' emotional connection towards the coffee shop is the location which is related to the school attended. That makes location or the school attended a primary element in building a business; locations that are easily accessible make it easy for the consumers to visit the business directly (Maranatha *et al.*, 2023).

3.2.2. Significant Relationships

Hypothesis Statement: H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between customer loyalty and customer engagement in terms of:

- Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC),
- Customer Engagement Emotional/Affective (CEE), and
- Customer Engagement Behavioral (CEB)?
- *Decision: H₀₃ NOT Accepted* in terms of overall Customer Engagement and Customer Loyalty, CEC, CEE, and CEB.

The fifth statement of the problem is the relationship between customer loyalty and engagement. Customer engagement emotional obtained the highest correlation, 0.911, and is the most influential factor among the three dimensions in fostering customer loyalty. All the dimensions show strong positive correlations with customer loyalty, garnering a 0.904 coefficient for the customer engagement cognitive, while the customer engagement behavioral has a 0.901 coefficient. This suggests that all three dimensions are significant at the 0.01 level.

The results relate to the study of Li *et al.* (2020). Customer engagement is essential to customer loyalty. Customer engagement is essential in forming customer loyalty (Parihar *et al.*, 2019; Kosiba *et al.*, 2018; Moliner *et al.*, 2018; Thakur, 2016; Kumar *et al.*, 2013). Several past studies have observed a direct effect of customer engagement on customer experience and loyalty (Arrfat, 2020; Safitri *et al.*, 2020). Engaged customers are loyal customers (Woodland, 2024). According to Bowden (2019), customer engagement is the mental process that becomes the instrument to gain new customers, which leads to customer loyalty. Customers more involved in brand relationships are likelier to be loyal, which can benefit the organization (Kaur *et al.*, 2020). The higher the level of customer engagement, the higher the customer loyalty (Rather, 2019). The company needs to build strong engagement with the customers to get more loyal customers (Li and Chen, 2020; Hollebeek, 2011). Customer loyalty can benefit the company because it shows the customers' engagement and positive attitude toward the product by repurchasing it (Bergel *et al.*, 2019). Customer engagement is anticipated to contribute to customer loyalty (Verhoef *et al.*, 2010), and the potential contribution is now transpiring in the literature and is still under research (Bowden, 2009). Customer engagement generates behavioral outcomes such as advocacy and intention of loyalty (Sashi *et al.*, 2019; Harrigan *et al.*, 2017; So *et al.*, 2016; and So *et al.*, 2014). Customer engagement increases customer loyalty due to increasing customer engagement, which creates customer satisfaction with the products (Arief *et al.*, 2019). Customers with whom the brand engages are likelier to show commitment, emotional bonding, trust, satisfaction, and loyalty toward the brand (Brodie *et al.*, 2013). Cognitive engagement is the relationship with the brand through the positive customer experience that keeps the customers loyal (Zhang and Xu, 2019). According to So *et al.* (2014), customer engagement is the customers' connection to the product manifested in cognitive, emotional, and behavioral responses outside the purchase. These types of engagement will result in customer loyalty. Building customer engagement can result in loyalty, commitment, satisfaction, and trust from the customers in the product (Li *et al.*, 2020; Hollebeek, 2011). Cognitive engagement is the customers' perception evaluation; examples are physical, affective, mental, and behavioral. It is associated with the customers' level of loyalty towards the brand by their attentiveness (Hwang *et al.*, 2019; Ahn and Back, 2018). Customer engagement cognitive and emotional dimensionally has been accepted and found in several studies to affect customer loyalty positively (Rasoolimanesh *et al.*, 2021; Harrigan *et al.*, 2018). Customers will grow an emotional attachment to the brand, which leads to the emergence of loyalty to the brand (Ferreira *et al.*, 2019; Huang, 2017). Emotional engagement results in loyalty (Newman and Patel, 2004). Customer engagement emotional can increase the loyalty, trust, and experience of the customers and their interaction with the brand (Chairunnisa and Ruswanti, 2023). Customer engagement behavior studies show that the more engaged customers are with the brand, the more likely they are to be loyal (Pansari and Kumar, 2016). The higher the customer to be more inclined by the brand, the higher the behavioral engagement, intelligent experiences, and customer loyalty Fan *et al.*, (2020). Behavioral engagement is customers' habitual or unconscious behavior that makes them loyal (Ni *et al.*, 2020). Behavioral engagement is the behavioral manifestation of motivational drivers; other than just purchasing, it is reflected by levels of behaviors, sharing, learning, endorsement,

and loyalty (Dessart *et al.*, 2016). Behavioral engagement results from repurchasing and regular visitation, which makes them loyal (Rather, 2020). Behavioral engagement involves customers promoting the brand's relationship with the people they work with or their friends, stimulating development that increases motivation and customer loyalty (Permadi and Silalahi, 2021). According to Van Doorn *et al.* (2010), customer engagement behavioral is the manifestation beyond purchase that results in motivational drivers toward the brand, making the customers loyal. Customer engagement behavioral goes beyond transactions. The manifestation results in repurchase, firm focus, and customer loyalty (Verleye *et al.*, 2014; Van Doorn *et al.*, 2010).

3.2.3. Significant Influence

- *Hypothesis Statement: H₀₄*: There is no significant influence between customer loyalty and customer engagement in terms of:
- Customer Engagement Cognitive (CEC),
- Customer Engagement Emotional/Affective (CEE), and
- Customer Engagement Behavioral (CEB)?
- *Decision: H₀₄* was NOT accepted in terms of customer loyalty, CEC, CEE, CEB, Customer Loyalty, and overall Customer Engagement.

The sixth statement of the problem is the influence of customer loyalty and customer engagement where it identifies customer engagement emotional as the strongest predictor of loyalty with ($\beta = 0.411$), followed by customer engagement behavioral ($\beta = 0.316$) and customer engagement cognitive ($\beta = 0.245$), all with p-values of 0.000. The analysis confirms that each engagement type significantly impacts customer loyalty, with emotional engagement being the most influential. This suggests enhancing emotional connections could be key to fostering loyalty among iced coffee shop customers.

The results relate to the study of Rasoolimanesh *et al.* (2019), customer engagement influences customer loyalty. Customer engagement positively influences customer loyalty (Paramita and Riorini, 2023). Customer engagement significantly affects customer loyalty (Al-Dmour, 2019; Hapsari *et al.*, 2017; Thakur, 2016; Hapsari *et al.*, 2015; and Brodie *et al.*, 2013). Customer engagement positively influences customer loyalty (Abror *et al.*, 2019). According to Sharma (2024), effective customer engagement in coffee shops will significantly increase customer loyalty. Customer engagement significantly and positively affects customer loyalty (Dhasan and Aryupong, 2019). Customer engagement positively influences customer loyalty (Harimurti and Suryani, 2019). Customer engagement positively affects customer loyalty (Kaur *et al.*, 2020). Customer engagement cognitive and emotional dimensionally has been accepted and found in several studies to affect customer loyalty positively (Rasoolimanesh *et al.*, 2021; Harrigan *et al.*, 2018). According to Simanjuntak *et al.* (2020), when consumers use or consume the same product, if they have a good emotional connection, consumers will be more inclined to buy the same product again. Customers' affective engagement positively affects investigating customer loyalty (Bergel and Brock, 2019). Customer engagement emotional significantly influences customer loyalty (Lin and Chao, 2023). Fostering emotional connection will further increase the consumers' preferences, trust and the repurchase behavior (Zeqiri *et al.*, 2023; Miao *et al.*, 2022; Asti *et al.*, 2021). Behavioral engagement is the energy, effort, and time spent on the brand during the interaction (Hollebeek *et al.*, 2014). It influences the customer experience and customer loyalty during the interaction and is the behavioral response of the customers (Rodrigues and Brandão, 2021; Trivedi and Sama, 2021; Hussein, 2018; Zarantonello and Schmitt, 2010; Brakus *et al.*, 2009). The anchored and supporting theories which are the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) Theory, supported by the Affective-Behavioral-Cognitive (ABC) Model and Self-Determination Theory (SDT). These theories provide a framework linking customer engagement and customer loyalty. In the SOR Theory, the results reveal that customer engagement dimensions (cognitive, emotional, and behavioral) strongly correlate with and predict customer loyalty, consistent with the SOR theory's evidence that external stimuli (e.g., brand experience) produce emotional and cognitive responses leading to observable behaviors. Emotional engagement, as the strongest predictor of loyalty ($\beta = 0.411$, $p < 0.01$), highlights the organism's role in processing stimuli, aligning with Mehrabian and Russell's model. Also, in the ABC Model, the findings confirm that attitudes toward iced coffee shops—shaped by emotions, thoughts, and actions—play a significant role in loyalty. Emotional engagement's dominance among the predictors supports the model's emphasis on affective components influencing behavior. The strong correlations between cognitive engagement ($r = 0.904$) and behavioral engagement ($r = 0.901$) further validate the ABC model's integrative framework. The results of the SDT suggest its relevance in linking intrinsic motivation to customer behavior, as engagement behaviors reflect autonomy, competence, and relatedness. However, emphasizing emotional connections indicates that external influences (e.g., environmental stimuli and marketing) might overshadow intrinsic motivations, slightly diverging from SDT's focus on psychological needs. The results largely support the theoretical framework, as the core tenets of SOR theory and the ABC model are strongly reflected in customer engagement and loyalty patterns. While SDT offers valuable insights, its role appears secondary to the emotionally driven mechanisms highlighted by the findings.

Future research might explore deeper integrations of SDT's motivational constructs with engagement behaviors. Overall, the results affirm the framework's relevance in explaining customer engagement and loyalty dynamics.

4. Conclusion

This study reveals that most iced coffee shop customers in Valencia City are female students aged 18 to 20 years, primarily from Valencia Colleges (Bukidnon), Inc., with 2nd-year students forming the largest group. Don Macchiatos emerged as the most popular iced coffee shop among respondents. The findings highlight that gender and age significantly influence customer engagement and loyalty, with emotional engagement being the strongest predictor of loyalty, followed by behavioral and cognitive factors. These insights support the anchor theory, emphasizing that fostering emotional connections enhances customer retention and business success. This study benefits society by providing coffee shop owners with actionable strategies to improve customer engagement and loyalty, contributing to sustainable business growth and improved customer experiences.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declares no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

The identity and data gathered from the participants was kept confidential to protect the respondents' rights and welfare. The researcher gave the participants consent, giving them the freedom to decline participation in the survey. Before answering the survey, the researchers are explained the study. Participants were instructed to be honest in their answers for more accurate results.

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